

Benefits Of Copper Sulphate in Poultry

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Abstract

Copper (Cu) is an essential trace element that plays an important role as a cofactor in numerous enzymatic reactions. They are involved in energy metabolism, anti-oxidant defense system, pigmentation, maturity, and stability of collagen and elastin. An appropriate level of Cu plays an important role in immune function as it promotes the reaction of pro and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Increased synthesis of the immune-regulatory system produces the stimulatory effect of copper on cellular and humoral immune mechanisms. Poultry diets often exceed the mandated Cu content for classical nutrition of 8 to 20 mg/kg due to the growth-promoting effect and the reduction of cholesterol in chicken meat imported by higher dietary levels such as 125 to 250 mg / Kg. copper supplement in the poultry diet has been shown to suppress lipid peroxidation by increased superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione, which minimize the adverse effects of reactive oxygen species thereby affecting the nutritive value, taste, and color of chicken meat.

Introduction

Among the trace elements, copper is necessary for the life and proper nutrition of farm animals. Especially chicken, cattle, and pigs. The trace elements added to feed are as pure as possible to ensure that the nutrition of animals is healthy and balanced to increase the quality of the finished products of the food industry. Copper act as a critical co-factor in multiple enzyme systems, integral to energy metabolism, tissue growth, RBC formation, defense, and immune competence. Copper is an essential element in cells; it can act as both a recipient and a donor of electrons. Excess of copper ions in cells is harmful because these generate free radicals and increase oxidative stress. Copper metabolism in multicellular organisms involves uptake, distribution, sequestration, and excretion at both the cellular and systemic levels.

Chelated Copper - Local Effects in Gut

1. Increasing gut-breaking strength.
2. Increased villi height and height with ratio.
3. The decreased gut depth and crypt depth/villus height ratio.
4. Decreased muscular layer thickness.

In Broilers

1. Chelated Cu improved body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR).
2. It will improve local cell-mediated immune response.
3. It will reduce the incidence of moderate and severe woody breasts in broilers (at 42 days of age).
4. Improve footpad lesions of wound healing

Mode Of Action of Copper

Dietary Cu is absorbed in the ilial region of the small intestine and then transported to the liver which acts as a major storehouse of Cu and from there to other extrahepatic tissue via ceruloplasmin. After that liver will

recycle Cu to the gut through its bile secretion which will either make it reabsorbed and exhibit some gut health benefits or excrete if it's in excess which may raise some economic concern.

Copper Deficiency

Copper deficiency results in anemia, growth depression, depigmentation of feathers, and diarrhea. Bones are fragile and easily broken. In turkey, it can lead to the rupture of the aorta. The biochemical lesion in the copper-deficient aorta is likely related to the failure to synthesize desmosine in the cross-link precursor of elastin. The lysine content of copper-deficient elastin is three times that seen in control birds, suggesting failure to incorporate lysine into the desmosine molecules.

As A Feed Additive

Acidified CuSo₄ for chickens has always been working as an anti-fungal and mold inhibitor feed supplement. FCR is Very much improved in Broilers and Layers when the feed is incorporated with poultry copper supplements. Due to the increased incidence of the rate of disease in the poultry population, the CuSo₄ supplement in feed is highly recommended to serve Cu supplements in water, So that it gets dissolved and taken by the bird easily. Recently, In poultry farming, acidified CuSo₄ is widely used against anemia and Improves the FCR.

Copper Vs Gizzard

The addition of CuSo₄ (about 200mg per kg) to conventional diets produced a variable growth response & improved feed conversion in broilers maintained under commercial conditions. Broilers' feed diets containing greater concentrations of Cu (b/w 400 & 600 mg/kg) exhibited reduced growth rate and feed intake. This is due to the lining of the gizzard getting damaged when a diet containing 600mg CuSo₄/ kg. The damage was a massive increase in the shedding of the gizzard glandular cells into the koilin layer and cessation of koilin production and also an increase in cellular desquamation.

Koilin layer

Conclusion

The supplementation of copper has become more common among poultry producers to its well-known beneficial effects on bird performance. Copper can serve to reduce disease challenges and boost immune functions. However, there are differences among sources of supplemental copper for both the bird and the environment. Feed manufacturers should take care to use copper and other minerals sources that will maximize animal health while minimizing the mineral output in waste.

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